

Phytochemicals, heavy metals and antioxidant studies on *Semecarpus anacardium* Linn. (fruit)

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Abstract : The main objective of the study is to focus on phytochemicals (physicochemical, HPTLC analysis, proximate analysis), heavy metals estimation and antioxidant studies on fruit of *Semecarpus anacardium* Linn. HPTLC method showed that the conc. of catechol in *Semecarpus anacardium* fruit is 0.082% (w/w). The concentration of Cu, Cr, Mn, Zn, Fe, Ni in plant sample were found to 7.71 ppm, 1.13 ppm, 27.25 ppm, 37.51 ppm, 87.71 ppm and 3.71 ppm, respectively whereas Pb and Cd were below detection limit. The proximate analysis showed the percentages of moisture content, ash content, crude protein, crude fibre, crude fat and carbohydrate of *Semecarpus anacardium* fruit as 10.15, 3.21, 8.41, 12.64, 5.30 and 74.87%, respectively while its calorific value is 332.63 kcal/100 g. Free radical scavenging abilities of the methanolic extracts were found to 56.98% by the DPPH method.

Keywords : *Semecarpus anacardium* fruit, phytochemical, heavy metals, HPTLC, proximate, antioxidant.

Introduction

Semecarpus anacardium Linn. (Family : Anacardiaceae) is commonly known as “Bhilwa” is a moderate sized deciduous tree found in the Himalayas and hotter parts of India up to 3500 ft. height^{1,2}. The fruit is reported to be caustic, astringent, alterative, antirheumatic, carminative, counterirritant, rubefacient and vesicant. It is also used in anorexia, cough, asthma, indigestion, enlargement of the spleen, alopecia, ulcers, corns, leprosy, leucoderma, rheumatism, piles and for various nervous diseases³⁻⁹. The fruits are also used as a dye. The crushed seeds are applied to cuts, bruises and scratches to stop bleeding. The oil is applied to cracks and fissures in the tails and hooves of animals. “Bhilwa” fruits are cooked in mustered oil and then applied to sores to kill maggots^{10,11}. The present communication deals with the detailed phytochemical, heavy metals and antioxidant evaluation on fruit sample by WHO – recommended physicochemical determinations and authentic phytochemical procedures. The physicochemical and phytochemical parameters presented in this paper may be proposed as parameters to establish the authenticity of *S. anacardium* fruit. HPTLC analysis showed the presence of catechol as a marker

compound in methanolic extract of the sample. A detailed heavy metal analysis has also been carried out for quantitative evaluation of heavy metals because WHO recommends that medicinal plants which form the raw materials for the finished products may be checked for the presence of heavy metals. Further, it regulates maximum permissible limits of toxic metals like As, Cd and Pb, which amount to 1.0, 0.3 and 10 ppm, respectively (WHO, 1989, 1998). The proximate analysis showed its high nutritional significance as food supplement. The antioxidant potential of *S. anacardium* fruit sample has also been studied by the DPPH method.

Results and discussion

Determinations of various physicochemical constants were carried out according to the methods provided in Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India (API). Physicochemical values, viz. LOD, total ash, acid-insoluble ash, water-soluble ash, extractives values (hexane, alcohol and water) are observed. The determination of the percentage of active constituents in crude drug is mentioned on air-dried basis so that the moisture content should be determined and should be controlled. In the case of *S. anacardium*

fruit, it was found to be 10.15% (Fig. 1). The total ash (3.21%), acid insoluble ash (0.16%) and water-soluble ash (1.58%) are considered to be important and useful parameters for detecting the presence of inorganic substances like silicate ion. Similarly the hexane (40.0%), alcohol (38.16%) and water-soluble extractives (9.50%) are indicators of the total solvent-soluble components (Fig. 1).

Quantitative estimation of primary metabolites showed the presence of tannins (0.03%), total phenolics (0.27%), flavonoids (2.15%), sugars (13.12%) and starch (9.03%) (Fig. 1). Successive extractive values were also determined and found that the hexane-soluble (31.13%), chloroform-soluble (1.17%), acetone-soluble (2.87%), ethanol-soluble (3.12%) and water-soluble extractives (17.59%) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Quantitative physicochemical analysis of *Semecarpus anacardium* fruit.

Fig. 2. Successive soxhlet extractive values of *Semecarpus anacardium* fruit.

On quantitative HPTLC analysis showed that catechol was present in *Semecarpus anacardium* fruit is 0.082% (w/w) concentration. Concentration of essential and non-essential heavy metals in medicinal plants beyond permissible limit is a matter of great concern to public safety all over the world. The problem is rather more serious in India, because medicinal plants which form the raw materials for the finished products are neither controlled nor properly regulated by quality assurance parameters. Quantitative estimation of heavy metal analysis are appended (Table 1). As evident from the table, maximum concentration of Fe is 87.71 ppm and minimum concentration of Cr is 1.13 ppm in fruit sample.

Table 1. Heavy metal concentration (ppm) in *Semecarpus anacardium* fruit

Heavy metal	Metal concentration (ppm)
Cu	7.71 ± 0.06
Cr	1.13 ± 0.02
Mn	27.25 ± 0.05
Zn	37.51 ± 0.03
Fe	87.71 ± 0.16
Ni	3.71 ± 0.02
Pb	BDL
Cd	BDL

BDL : Below detection limit.

The proximate analysis showed the percentages of moisture content, ash content, crude protein, crude fibre, crude fat and carbohydrate of the *Semecarpus anacardium* fruit as 10.15, 3.21, 8.41, 12.64, 5.30 and 74.87%, respectively while its calorific value is 332.63 kcal/100 g (Table 2). This shows its high nutritional value as food supplement.

Free radical-scavenging abilities of the extracts were found to 56.98% which is significantly less than those of

Table 2. Proximate and chemical analysis of *Semecarpus anacardium* Linn. (fruit)

Constituents	Value (%)
Moisture	10.15
Ash	3.21
Protein	8.41
Fat	5.30
Carbohydrate	74.87
Crude fibre	12.64
Energy (kcal)	332.63

ascorbic acid (68.60%) and quercetin (67.94%) (Fig. 6). The study showed that the extracts have the proton-donating ability and could serve as free radical inhibitor or scavengers, acting possibly as primary antioxidants. Polyphenols are the major plant compounds with antioxidant activity. This activity is believed to be mainly due to their redox properties, which play an important role in adsorbing and neutralizing free radicals, quenching singlet and triplet oxygen or decomposing peroxides.

The present work was taken up with a view to lay down standards which will contribute significantly to quality control of these medicinally useful *Semecarpus anacardium* fruit. Heavy metal analysis suggest that medicinal plants used for human consumption or for preparation of herbal products and standardized extracts should be collected from an unpolluted natural habitat. The proximate analysis showed its high nutritional significance as food supplement. Antioxidant activity of fruit showed that extract have the proton-donating ability and could serve as free radical inhibitor. Above study on this species may be useful to industries for the commercial exploitation with pharmaceutical and nutraceutical attributes to herbal formulations.

Experimental

(i) Collection of plant material :

In the present study, plant materials were collected from Himalayan region of India and were authenticated by Dr. A. K. S. Rawat, Head, Pharmacognosy and Ethnopharmacology Division, National Botanical Research Institute, Lucknow (India). Herbarium specimens were prepared and deposited (Field voucher no. 262510) to the National Herbarium of the Institute.

(ii) Physicochemical and phytochemical evaluation :

Physicochemical and phytochemical parameters were calculated from shade-dried powdered material according to the recommended procedures¹²⁻¹⁴.

(iii) HPTLC studies :

A densitometry HPTLC analysis was also performed for the development of characteristic fingerprint profile, which may be used as marker for quality evaluation and standardization of the drug¹⁵.

(iv) Extraction of plant samples :

Accurately weighed 2.0 g of the coarse powder of

Fig. 3. HPTLC profile under UV-254 nm.

Semecarpus anacardium fruit were extracted separately with methanol (4×25 mL) under reflux (30 min each time) on water bath. The combined extracts were filtered, mixed and concentrated on rotavapor. The syrupy com-

pounds were evaporated to dryness on a freeze-drier and 10 mg/mL solutions were prepared with AR grade methanol.

(v) *Preparation of standard solution :*

1 mg of catechol was dissolved in 1 ml of methanol to prepare 1 mg/ml of standard solution.

(vi) *Procedure :*

8 and 10 μ L of the standard solution and 10 μ L of test solution were applied on a precoated silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ TLC plate (E. Merck) of 0.2 mm thickness. The plate was developed in the solvent system till the solvent rise to a height of 80 mm.

(vii) *Chromatographic conditions :*

Toluene : ethyl acetate : formic acid (8 : 2 : 0.1 v/v) was used as mobile phase in a Camag twin-trough chamber (20 cm \times 10 cm) previously saturated with mobile phase vapour for 10 min : Room temperature was 28 °C. After removal of plates from chamber completely dried

Fig. 4. HPTLC densitometric scan (at 254 nm) of catechol as marker compound.

Fig. 5. HPTLC densitometric scan (at 254 nm) of *Semecarpus anacardium* fruit.

Fig. 6. DPPH % free radical inhibition of *Semecarpus anacardium* fruit vs conc.

with dryer and catechol was simultaneously quantified by using CAMAG TLC Scanner model-3 equipped with winCATS [version 3.2.1] Software (Figs. 3, 4 and 5).

The following scan conditions were applied slit width – 4×0.45 nm, wavelength (λ_{\max} – 254 nm), absorption – reflection scan mode.

(viii) Heavy metal analysis :

(a) Acid digestion of plant samples :

Weighed quantities of crushed and powdered portion of plant sample in a china dish were heated in an oven at 110 °C to remove moisture. Then the dried sample after charring, was heated in a furnace for 4 h at 550 °C. The contents of china dish were cooled in desiccator and 2.5 mL 6 M HNO₃ was added in to the dish to dissolve its contents. The solution was filtered and transferred to a 20 ml flask and diluted to the mark¹⁶.

Estimation of heavy metals was carried on Flame Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer [FAAS] (Polarised Zeeman Hitachi 2000 was used).

(b) Calibration of equipment :

For the elements under investigation we established the following sensitivity and detection limits, respectively of the used FAAS apparatus : Pb 0.2 and 1.0 ppm, Cr 0.5 and 3.0 ppm, Cd 0.2 and 1.0 ppm, Fe 0.5 and 5.0 ppm, Cu 0.5 and 3.0 ppm, Mn 0.5 and 2.50 ppm, Zn 0.05 and 5.0 ppm, Ni 0.5 and 4.0 ppm.

(ix) Proximate and chemical analysis :

Air-dried (35–40 °C) powdered corm (100 mesh) of *Semecarpus anacardium* fruit were taken. The moisture contents were determined by drying the sample at 105 °C in the oven up to constant weight. The crude protein value of the sample was assessed by determining the total organic nitrogen using micro-Kjeldahl's apparatus. The crude lipids were extracted in petroleum ether at 40 to 60 °C using soxhlet apparatus and then evaporating the solvent up to dryness by using rotary evaporator¹⁷. For the estimation of the fiber contents, the dry outcome of lipid estimation was ignited and the ash contents were determined and taken as equivalent to fiber contents¹⁸. Carbohydrate contents of each sample were calculated using the difference method as follows : Carbohydrate (%) = 100 - (moisture (%) + protein percentage (%) + lipid (%) + ash contents (%)) whereas, the energy values of each sample were determined using the following formula. K calories/100 g = 9 (crude fats (%)) + 4 (carbohydrates (%) + proteins (%)).

(x) Determination of in vitro antioxidant activity :

The effects of free radical scavenging activity by

methanolic extracts of *Semecarpus anacardium* fruit processed by DPPH method¹⁶. To evaluate antioxidant activity, solution of 0.135 mM DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) in methanol was prepared and 1.0 mL of this solution was mixed with 1.0 mL of extract in methanol containing 0.02–0.1 mg of the extract. The reaction mixture was vortexed thoroughly and left in the dark at room temperature for 30 min. The absorbance of the mixture was measured at 517 nm using Double beam UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Thermo Electron Corporation, Cambridge, England). Ascorbic acid and quercetin were used as reference standards. The ability to scavenge DPPH radical was calculated by the following equation¹⁹.

DPPH radical scavenging activity (%) =

$$[(\text{Abs}_{\text{control}} - \text{Abs}_{\text{sample}})/(\text{Abs}_{\text{control}})] \times 100$$

where Abs_{control} is the absorbance of DPPH radical + methanol; Abs_{sample} is the absorbance of DPPH radical + sample extract/standard.

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